

MEASURES TO PRESENT AND MOVE FURNITURE IN THE PRODUCTION ENTERPRISE IN THE FOREIGN MARKET

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

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Abstract. *In this article, the main emphasis in the formation of the export product strategy of the enterprise is placed on the effective formation and management of the product range, the timely provision of a set of products that most fully meets the needs of consumers.*

Keywords: *furniture, complex, quality, strategy, product policy, export, foreign market.*

Introduction. In the third priority of the Development Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2022-2026, rapid development of the national economy and ensuring high growth rates, "... creation of conditions for the organization of entrepreneurial activity and formation of permanent sources of income, the share of the private sector in the gross domestic product to 80 percent and increasing its share in exports to 60 percent. Improving the activity of existing structures for supporting entrepreneurship, reducing unemployment and poverty in the regions" such priority tasks are also considered as one of the guarantees for the development of small business and private entrepreneurship.

Along with saturating the market of our country with goods, private entrepreneurship makes a great contribution to creating new jobs, obtaining additional income, and increasing the welfare of the people. As the President of our country, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, said, "If the people are rich, the state will be rich and strong."

A number of decrees and decisions of the President of our country are devoted to the development and comprehensive support of entrepreneurship. Among these, it is possible to include Decree No. PF-5718 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated May 14, 2019 "On measures to radically improve the system of support and protection of business activities". The important aspect of this Decree is that it was emphasized that there are several negative factors preventing the wider and active involvement of the population in business activities, primarily due to the lack of a practical and transparent system of communication between state bodies and entrepreneurs, and an effective mechanism for eliminating this situation was defined.

Analysis of literature on the topic. Based on foreign experiences, it should be noted that many economists have been engaged in the development of marketing principles and their practical application. Among them, we can include famous scientists such as F. Kotler, M. Porter, D. Evans, I. Ansoff, M. Berman, M. Golubkov, P. Samuelson, D. Marshall.

It is necessary to acknowledge the scientists who made a great contribution to the development of the marketing theory in the economy, while the researches conducted in the field of marketing in our country for many years are based on national characteristics. These include M. Mukhammedov, M. Pardaev, R. Ibragimov, Yo. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhojaev, B. Khodiev, D. Rakhimova, R. Boltaboev, D. Ergashkhodjaeva and others can be included.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. It is to determine the ways of scientifically and methodologically justifying the introduction of the concept of international marketing service development in furniture production enterprises.

To achieve this goal, the following tasks were defined and fulfilled in the scientific article:

Researching the essence and modern forms of the marketing concept;

Researching the content of marketing services, the theory of their organization, their place and features in the economy;

Analysis of the current state of the furniture industry and the activities of the international marketing service;

To offer new approaches of international marketing service in the field of furniture production;

Development of proposals for the formation of regional international marketing services in the furniture industry based on the experience of our country and foreign companies.

In international marketing, the product policy is the central element of the marketing complex - an integral part of the international marketing policy in relation to the product. Brand strategy, product quality, assortment, packaging, branding, design, branding and service are components of brand policy in international marketing[1].

The most important part of the company's international product policy is the sum of adaptation and standardization of goods to foreign market conditions. In international marketing, it is possible to distinguish four principle directions of the policy corresponding to the brand strategy:

normal expansion (export);

product customization;

"reverse" inventions or new inventions;

stop production of goods.

A simple expansion or export strategy implies a standard approach to the export range of the enterprise. In this case, the enterprise produces and sells domestic goods in the foreign market as well. In this case, none of the aspects of product development (product description, packaging and appearance) will be changed and adapted to the conditions of the foreign market. A simple expansion strategy is used by the company when sales in the domestic market do not bring commercial success. The enterprise makes a decision to enter the foreign market when there are signs of a decrease in sales volume in the domestic market. In order to save all costs in promoting the product to the foreign market, the company uses a simple expansion strategy.

In the formation of the company's export product strategy, the main attention is focused on the effective formation and management of the product assortment, on the timely offer of a set of products that most fully satisfy the needs of consumers.

Product adaptation strategy consists of product modification taking into account the characteristics of the foreign market and environment. Adaptation not only to product specifications (quality, appearance), but also to its packaging and service may also apply to display. Table 1 examines four options for product modification [2].

A complete standardization strategy is used in two cases. The first case is episodic export, that is, the producer is "forced" to export the product by a foreign buyer (intermediary) who wants to buy the product from this manufacturer. The second option refers to large transnational corporations that mass produce basic essential products (mainly food products).

Table 1

The main options for modification of furniture products

Communication	Goods	
	The product does not change	The product changes
Standard communication	Complete standardization (communication and merchandise)	Product modification
Variable communication	Communication links modification	Communication links and commodity modification

The choice of communication modification strategy can be justified by the fact that the same product can have different functions and satisfy the needs of different markets. In developed countries, it is considered a sport. In this regard, the advertising appeal should be different in both cases. The need for adaptation of communication links is mainly related to the national-cultural and socio-economic characteristics of the market [3].

The product modification strategy is used when the product is designed for the same purpose in all markets, but the conditions of its use are different.

Communication and brand modification strategies require significant costs. Therefore, only large and powerful companies that have financial support or serve large customers are able to implement it.

When choosing between adaptation and standardization strategies, it is necessary to make an economic calculation of their effectiveness, for example, comparing the costs of using product modification strategies of the manufacturing firm with the benefits obtained from using a particular modification. There are also a number of factors that require modification regardless of the wishes of the exporting firm:

- official requirements (main standards of the product in this country); tariffs;
- national protectionist policies (many governments require domestic production of products to create jobs and boost domestic industry);
- technical reasons: the requirements of some consumers can be met without adapting the technical decision (changing the diameter, design and color of the car piston);
- specific features of the local tax system; climatic conditions.

At the international level, the goal of quality policy is the "globalization" of the national product or the development of original products for the foreign market [4]. A number of groups of factors affecting the company's quality policy can be distinguished when adapting goods to the foreign market:

- legal restrictions;
- perceived quality level of consumed goods; product consumption description;
- sales channels; service companies;
- level of integration of the country into the world economy;
- areas where the product can be used.

Each exporter tries to increase the competitiveness of his goods on the foreign market, that is, to gain the opportunity to be selected by a foreign buyer from among the goods of other sellers that are in demand in a particular market.

"HAVAS" LLC has several options for organizing sales in the foreign market, their use requires different levels of preparation:

- Trading through dealers.
- Organization of a trading house.
- Opening a representative office abroad.
- Conclusion of a contract on joint production.

In the international furniture trade, the exporter of goods should develop a leadership psychology by creating competitive goods that meet current and prospective requirements and serve to increase his reputation.

The competitiveness of export goods is determined by consumer characteristics and technological indicators, and this series includes, first of all, clearly defined direction, high technical level, level of preparation, reliability, simplicity, convenient weight, size and beautiful design, selling price, attractive service, consumer value (repair, maintenance and operation costs) can be included.

Moving the products of "HAVAS" LLC in the foreign market requires the formation of a system of marketing communications. As indicated above, the export of furniture products to the foreign market requires product certification, preparation for customs clearance, and logistics systems. At the same time, supporting the sale of goods remains an important task of the enterprise, because the objectives of the enterprise in the foreign market may not coincide with the objectives of local sellers. In our opinion, starting export from promising markets to Tajikistan and Kazakhstan requires practical measures in the following directions (Chart 1).

Drawing 1. Marketing communications of "HAVAS" LLC

In this case, the competitiveness of the product means, in addition to its compliance with the market requirements, it also means the ability to resist similar products of competitors. From time to time, it is necessary to evaluate the current and future competitiveness of the product, to make a decision about its production for export in the future, to modernize the product on the market or to remove it and introduce a new product. In international trade, it is necessary for a company that exports goods to develop a leadership psychology by creating high-quality competitive goods oriented to current and future demand, increasing its reputation, and correctly directing it to the international market.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Developed at the request of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 **"Strategy of Actions" as a way to speed up the economy** "...assimilation of new types of products and technologies in principle, ensuring the competitiveness of national goods in domestic and foreign markets on this basis; "Continuing the policy of promoting the localization

of production and, first of all, replacing the import of consumer goods and components, expanding inter-sectoral industrial cooperation" have been defined.

"HAVAS COMFORT MEBEL" LLC chooses two ways in its marketing activities: a) to determine the wishes of the customer and study to what extent they are fulfilled during the order fulfillment period. This method is mainly used for individual orders, that is, furniture that is selected according to rooms, and as a result, the mass catalog is also extended to furniture; b) Meeting the needs of potential consumers based on the samples and catalogs available in the enterprise.

As a result of the conducted research, we developed the following proposals for the development of marketing research in the enterprise to increase the export potential:

Expanding the forms and scope of marketing services, i.e. applying functional, product and matrix structures, etc., widely used in market relations;

Implementation of the marketing outsourcing system in the marketing services system, i.e. implementation of marketing services with the help of external organizations;

Organization and development of marketing service based on digitization technology;

Extensive use of benchmarking information in marketing services, study of the results of others' experiments;

The effect of these offers is reflected not only in the volume of sales, but also in the reputation of the enterprise.

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